

Comparison of batch and SABRe in creating consistent oil-in-water emulsions

Case Study # 08, rev 3,
20 Nov 2021, By Samuel Adams

Formulation chemistry covers a large subject ranging from flavours and fragrances to food and beverages to agrichemicals and cosmetics. Although no chemical bonds are made or broken, formulation is a diverse field utilised across products found in everyday life.

Emulsions are one aspect of formulation chemistry that is of particular interest in foods, beverages and cosmetics. Emulsions occur where two immiscible liquids are mixed to form small bubbles, droplets, or micelles. In a majority of cases a third agent - a surfactant - is added to separate the two phases and stabilise large interfacial surface area in between the phases.

Emulsions can be found in a variety of products, from mayonnaise to face cream, where quality is determined by the size of the bubbles, the uniformity and the emulsions stability once formed.

Properties of emulsions, therefore, are determined by

- Chemistry of the interacting phases
- Properties and amount of the surfactant
- Mixing of the components

Dispersion of air bubbles as a demonstration for multiphase mixing in SABRe

The Experiment: batch vs flow comparison

Stoli Chem's SABRe (Scalable Agitated Baffle Reactor) was used to determine how the flow reactor performs against batch processing in liquid-liquid emulsion forming. The SABRe contains a series of 10 CSTRs (continuously stirred tank reactors) with stirrers in each chamber to ensure thorough mixing of the emulsion. The liquid feed is decoupled from the stirring to have a system that can have a low flow rate for example with a high mixing capability to ensure that the emulsification process is efficient. Using the SABRe for flow was performed a comparative study with a batch processed under identical conditions. A 3% commercial surfactant (sodium laureth sulfate) solution was fed into the reactor at a 20:1 volumetric ratio with oleic acid at a residence time of 20 minutes.

In the comparison batch experiment, 100 mL of the 3% commercial detergent solution and 5 mL oleic acid was stirred for 20 minutes. In both reactors, the stirring rates were 1,200 rpm. The resulting emulsions were sampled and analysed by optical microscopy.

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Droplet size distribution results

The microscopy image shows emulsions formed by the SABRe system compared with batch. These droplets were obtained under the same parameters – composition of the mixture, reactor volume, stirring rate and time.

In batch, there are occasional large droplets while the multi-CSTR SABRe produced much **smaller and more uniform droplets**.

Analysing 500+ individual droplet sizes in each emulsion, both reactors were compared quantitatively.

In agreement with the image above, the batch reactor produced larger droplets with a much broader size distribution, from 5 to over 100 µm. The SABRe system generated droplets in the size range of around 2 to 50 µm. The smaller droplet sizes are preferred as they translate into a smoother finished emulsion.

The average droplet size was almost half in SABRe compared to batch. Yet, a crucial parameter for the emulsions was also uniformity which was determined by calculation of the standard deviation which was dramatically smaller in the SABRe. Even in relative terms, the emulsions obtained in SABRe are twice as uniform as those in batch.

	BATCH	SABRe
Average droplet size (µm)	11.3	6.4
Standard deviation (µm)	25.3	7.4

The results show the superior performance of SABRe's multi-CSTR reactor design compared with batch. Along with the faster processing benefits of continuous production performance, the **exceptional mixing** performance in SABRe translates to **2-fold reduction in size and uniformity** of the emulsions.

The SABRe system (available in steel, Hastelloy or glass) is suitable for a wide range of chemical applications. Combining simplicity with superb reaction control, SABRe is the best choice for simple, safe and cost effective chemistry.

What can the SABRe do for you today? Get in touch and arrange a trial.

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